

Nordex Group

Acceptance Criteria of DNV RP-0661

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INTRODUCTION

- > Our Goal:
 - > Use LIDAR TI for onshore site suitability

- > Our Issues:
 - > Customers provide met mast (MM) and LIDAR data with distances of 100m to 1000m
 - > Not crucial for machine learning corrected TI regarding fatigue load estimators
 - > BUT crucial for the acceptance criterion (RRMSE) of the DNV RP-0661

- > Our Analyses:
 - > Correction of LIDAR TI with machine learning algorithms
 - > Investigation of fatigue load estimators and acceptance criteria of DNV RP-0661 for co-located MMs:
 - > 5 sites considered with one reference met masts (RMM) and one temporary met mast (TMM)
 - > Distances between RMM and TMM: 200 to 325m

Acceptance Criteria of DNV RP-0661

SITE WITH LIDAR AND MM

- > RRMSE criterion is not fulfilled for this site
- > Damage Index of machine learning correction correlates well with Damage Index of MM
- > Time dependence is not needed for fatigue loads

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SITE WITH RMM AND TMM

- > RRMSE criterion is not fulfilled
- > Time dependence is not needed for fatigue loads
- > Time dependence is an issue for the RRMSE criterion
- > Damage Index of TMM correlate well with Damage Index of RMM, even in complex terrain
- > RRMSE criterion doesn't correlate well with fatigue relevant flow properties

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